

Integrated pest management – other pests

Effect of organic amendments in controlling rice root nematodes

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Rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae* is widespread throughout the rice-growing regions of India and causes economic loss to the crop. We evaluated seven organic amendments for rice root nematode control in field experiments in 1987 and 1988. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with three replications. Plots were 4 × 2.5 m.

The experimental fields were naturally infested with nematodes. Organic amendments were applied 7 d before transplanting (DT) 40-d-old Ponni

Rice root nematode population and grain yield after applying organic amendments.^a

Treatment	1987			Grain yield (kg/plot)	1988			Grain yield (kg/plot)
	Population (no./5 g root)				Population (no./5 g root)			
	30 DT	60 DT	90 DT		30 DT	60 DT	90 DT	
Press mud 10 t/ha	3.0	7.3	27.3	8.57	6.3	14.7	15.0	8.68
Farmyard manure 25 t/ha	10.0	17.0	31.3	7.52	14.0	22.0	24.0	7.58
Neem cake 1 t/ha	2.3	6.7	26.0	8.67	5.7	13.0	14.3	8.70
Coir waste 10 t/ha	15.3	19.0	33.3	6.98	19.0	27.0	25.7	7.07
Poultry manure 25 t/ha	9.0	15.7	30.0	7.58	13.7	22.0	23.3	7.67
Neem leaves 5 t/ha	5.7	11.7	29.3	8.00	11.0	18.3	19.2	8.07
<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> leaves 5 t/ha	5.6	12.7	28.0	8.00	10.0	19.0	22.0	7.77
Untreated control	18.0	25.3	37.0	6.65	24.3	29.7	27.0	6.85
LSD (0.05)	2.5	2.3	2.5	0.33	2.7	2.4	4.2	0.45

^aMeans of 3 replications. DT = days after transplanting.

seedlings at 15- × 10-cm spacing. Root samples were collected 30,60, and 90 DT. The nematode population was estimated by the Baermann pan technique, using 5 g roots/sample.

Neem cake at 1 t/ha and press mud at 10 t/ha significantly lowered nematode populations up to 60 DT (see table). *Calotropis* leaves and neem leaves at 5 t/ha were the next best treatments. ■

Farming systems

Simulation of soybean yield in a rice-based cropping system

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In the Cauvery Delta zone of Tamil Nadu, traditional rice fallow crops *Vigna mungo*, *Vigna radiata*, and *Glycine max* are grown in an area of about 1.63 million ha. Soybean is slowly being adopted as a rice fallow crop that requires less turnaround time. Soybean seeds are sown immediately after harvest of the preceding rice crop.

We used the SOYCROS model developed at IIRI to simulate the yield of soybean following rainfed lowland rice. The model was validated with data from a field experiment at TRRI Feb-Apr 1990. ADT1 was the soybean variety; IR20, the rice variety. Crop and weather data were inputs into the model.

Simulated and observed grain yield agreed satisfactorily for all sowing dates (see table). The attainable yield of soybean following rice under rainfed conditions can be reasonably predicted by the model, using local crop and weather data inputs.

Simulated and observed grain yield of soybean (ADT1) at TRRI, Aduthurai, India, 1990.

Sowing date	Yield (t/ha)		Agreement (%)
	Simulated	Observed	
1 Jan	1.0	0.9	90
2 Feb	0.8	0.7	88
1 Mar	0.2	0.3	120

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In the tables in the following issues of IRRN, replace the π with the \pm sign:

Aug 1990, p. 13

Oct, p. 7, 8

Dec, last column of the table on p. 20

In Table 2 on page 14 of the Aug issue, replace the asterisks in all columns with the multiplication (\times) sign.

On pages 28 and 29 of IRRN 15 (6) (Dec 1990), replace India in the titles of Table 1 and Table 2 with Pakistan. ■

ANNOUNCEMENT

New IIRI publications

Publication — a training manual, by I. Montagnes

Editing and publication — a handbook for trainers, by I. Montagnes

A farmer's primer on growing upland rice, by M.A. Arrau deau and B.S. Vergara (in Cebuano)

Human geography of rice in Southeast Asia, by R. E. Huke and E. H. Huke
Publications of international agricultural research and development centers: 1990 computer edition
Field problems of tropical rice (Lao edition)